

ICT BASED BEST PRACTICES IN LIBRARIES

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Abstract

The Present research paper discusses on the best and ICT Practices conducted in K.B.P. and M.V.P. College, Libraries in Islampur City from last 50 and 20 years, respectively. Karmveer Bhaurao Patil (Arts, Com.& Sc.) College, library and Malati Vasantdada Patil Kanya (Arts & Com) College, Library were established in the year 1961 and 1989 respectively. Both colleges conducted the following best and ICT Practices as per the NAAC indications. Some Special Best and ICT based practices followed by the both College libraries successfully, effectively and efficiently in the libraries as well as its impact on library use.

Key Word – College Library, Best and ICT Practices, Special Services, NAAC.

1. Introduction

Library and Information Services of Higher Education Institutions plays a vital role in enhancing the quality of academic and research environment. Library is the fulcrum of support for the entire range of academic activities on an educational campus. In Today's high-tech learning environment, the library as a learning resource is taking up increasingly more academic space and time in the life of a learner. This paper discusses on the Best and ICT based Best practices in the Karmveer Bhaurao Patil College library, Islampur and Malati Vasantdada Patil Kanya Mahavidyalaya, Islampur. Library and Information services are always helpful to increasing quality in higher education. NAAC is always trying to maintain the quality of colleges and universities. Library is the heart of every college and Institution, so wherever NAAC is evaluating the colleges and universities mainly focus on the library and information services but the library is the heart of the every colleges and universities because while re-evaluation of college NAAC pointed out of college development. NAAC specially mention some best practices in re-evaluation of colleges. It will help to bring library forwards. State Government of Maharashtra became the first state Government in the country to establish 'Quality Assurance Cell' in the Higher Education

Ministry to promote and push the concept of assessment and accreditation in colleges and universities. These both colleges established only for the rural area students. Both colleges submitted the SSR to NAAC Office, Bangalore for getting NAAC re-accreditation.

K.B.P. and M.V.P. College (Arts, Com. and Sc.)

Mahatma Phule Shikshan Sanstha, Islampur has been established the K.B.P. (Arts, Com & Sc.) College in the year 1961 at Islampur Taluka Walwa Dist Sangli. This area is famous for sugarcane production in Maharashtra. The library is functioning from the establishment of college and rendering the efficient and effective services which are the well known college in Maharashtra. In the Year of 2003 the NAAC Peer team was visited and awarded the B level gradation. The college running the further courses i.e. B.A., B.Com, B.Sc., B.C.A, B.C.S., B.Sc.IT, and B.Sc. Bio-technology and Post Graduate courses are i.e. M.A. (Marathi, Hindi, English, History, Economics and Psychology and M.Com.). More over college has YCMOU Study Centre for B.A., B.Com etc. This college affiliated to Shivaji University Kolhapur.

Walwa Taluka Education Society, Islampur has been established by the M.V.P.Kanya (Arts and Com.) College in the year 1989 at Islampur Taluka Walwa Dist Sangli. The library is functioning from the establishment of college and rendering the efficient and effective services to women education. In the year of 2004 the NAAC Peer team was visited and awarded the C++ level gradation. The college running the further courses i.e. B.A., B.Com, and Post Graduate courses are i.e. M.A. (Marathi, Hindi). This college affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

Department of Library Information Science.

The K.B.P. College library is known as the **Maharishi Vittal Ramaji Shinde Library** and Information Science. It is situated in the Independent Special library building. Library holds the more than 70,000 Books on different subjects. The subject's focus the four languages i.e. English, Marathi, Hindi and Sanskrit all social science subjects and science subjects' books are also available in the library. Philosophy subject and its books is the special feature of this college. The college library holds excellent collection on reference books. Presently, the library is functioning fully computerized and automated with Web OPAC. It has standard library software named as **easy and useful software** with online opac system. As the first step for introduction of bar coded in circulation control system it is

necessary that the holding the accession number and member identification are converted in to barcodes. Total 70 journal/ periodicals are available in the library. 250 CD collections on various subjects and 6,00 Bound Back Volumes of periodicals and journals from 1961 up to 2011.

The M.V.P. College library is known as the Malati Library and Information Science. Library holds **17,000** books on different subjects. The subject's focus the three languages i.e. English, Marathi and Hindi. All social science subjects' books are available in the library. Home Science subject and its collection is the special feature of this college. The college library holds excellent collection on reference books. Presently, the library is functioning partly computerized and automated. It has standard library software named as **SOUL software (Network Version)** with online opac system. Total 85 Journals/Periodicals are available in the library. The total 101 CD's collection of various subjects is available in the library. The total 555 Back Volumes of back issues of Journals and periodicals from the year 1990 to 2011.

Aims of the Study

1. To identify the best practices maintained by NAAC
2. To study the best practices followed by the K.B.P. and M.V.P. College Libraries, Islampur
3. To find out special best practices of both college libraries.

Limitation of the Study

This study is limited only to K.B.P. and M.V.P. College libraries, Islampur.

National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC)

The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) is an autonomous body established by the University Grants Commission (UGC) of India to assess and accredit institutions of higher education in the country. It is an outcome of the recommendations of the National Policy in Education (1986) that laid special emphasis on upholding the quality of higher education in India. The system of higher education in India has expanded rapidly during the last fifty years. There have been criticisms that the country has permitted the mushrooming of institutions of higher education with substandard facilities and consequent dilution of standards. To address the issues of deterioration in quality, the National Policy on Education (1986) and the Plan of Action (POA-1992) that spelt out the strategic plans for the

policies, advocated the establishment of an independent national accreditation body. Consequently, the NAAC was established in 1994 with its headquarters at Bangalore.

Vision and Mission

NAAC states that: The activities and plans of the NAAC are guided by its vision and mission that focus on making quality assurance an integral part of the functioning of higher education institutions. The vision of the NAAC is to make quality the defining element of higher education in India through a combination of self and external quality evaluation, promotion and sustenance initiatives. The mission statement of the NAAC defines the following key tasks:

Quality Indicators in Library and Information Services for College Libraries

NAAC has developed a set of objective indicators to facilitate assessment of library and

Information services in academic institutions. The guidelines are derived from an understanding of global developments, the national environment, and the outcome of a recent national-level workshop held at the NAAC, in which college and university librarians and library scholars from across the country had participated. College libraries need facilities that promote effective and interactive access and use of information resources for all users. In the area of physical facilities, libraries need safe, comfortable, well lighted, clean space, with adequate and appropriate seating, to ensure effective use of the library's resources. College libraries must consider study space needs, with special attention to reserve collections and the hostel environment of the institution. The libraries need well-framed rules and guidelines with regard to hours of access, circulation policies, and other regulations, to offer better services to users. Affiliated college libraries have the primary mission of meeting the library and information needs of undergraduate students. The guidelines below identify the principal factors influencing the development and maintenance of college library services and collections.

1. Management of library and information services.

According to the guidelines of NAAC, the core objective of the library in the degree colleges is to support the academic programmes offered. The library may design a system to delivery products and certain minimum infrastructure, such as book stacks, reading halls, circulation counter, and so on.

2. Collection and services provided to users.

The library is required to provide varied, authoritative, and up-to-date resources that supports its mission and fulfill the needs of its users. Resources may be provided in a variety of formats. A college library must have the quantity of resources prescribed by the UGC and other governing bodies. The library has a key role in supporting the academic activities of institutions. Assessment of college libraries must be carried out regularly to sustain and enhance their quality.

8. Best Practices Maintained by NAAC:

Listed below are some of NAAC best practices for enhancing the academic information environment and usability.

Management and administration of Library -

1. In Service Programme
2. Observation Of Other Library Practices
3. Staff Promotion Policy
4. Maintenance Of Service Areas
5. Special Deposit Scheme
6. Resource Generation
7. Student Internship Programme
8. Resources Generation Through Internet Services
9. Student Participation Programme
10. Earn While Learn Programme
11. Library Science As Optional Course Papers.

Collection and Services -

12. Compact Storage and less used collection
13. Collection development in different formats
14. Library book exhibition
15. Extended library opening hours
16. Extended hours of services
17. Collection enhancement in hybrid library

8.3. Extent of the Use of Services-

18. User Education (Information Literacy Programme)
19. Preparatory course for students' projects
- 20 User Orientations
22. Information aids

23. Course Module of LIS
24. Library Use Statistics
25. Library Best User Award
26. User Feedback practice through different formats
27. User feedback practice through suggestion boxes

8.4 Use of Information Technology

28. Online Information Retrieval
29. Free browsing unit
30. Broadband internet centre.
31. Library Homepage for Information dissemination
32. Dynamic library website
33. User feedback through the library homepage
34. 24/7 access to e-resources
35. Group confessionals night services offer
36. Access to digital repository through website
37. Digital documentary Services
38. Digital Repositories
39. CD mirror server facility
40. CD net server facility
41. Digization of Manuscripts
42. Multilingual, Integrated web enabled databases complete automation of the house services
43. Using self development integrated library software automation of in house services.
44. Web OPAC
45. Information Retrieval through Web OPAC.
46. LAN Facility
47. Database creation using international standard formats
48. Electronic surveillance system.

Best and ICT Best Practices Followed by K.B.P. and M.V.P. College, Libraries, Islampur

Library Users

The K.B.P. College holds **230** teaching and non teaching staff as the users, **5000** students of all disciplines. The other mother society members, society members, ex-students are the users. The MPSC Centre students are the regular users of the library. The Shivaji

University Distance Learning Center's students are the users. The M.V.P. College holds **30** teaching and non teaching staff as the users and **736** students of all disciplines. The other mother society members, society members, ex-students are the regular users of the library.

Library Staff

The K.B.P. College library holds Librarian-1, Assistant Librarian-1, Clerks-2 and Library Attendant-7. The Whole staff is appointed as per the Shivaji University, Kolhapur and Government of Maharashtra rules and regulations. The M.V.P. College library holds Librarian-1, Library Attendant-2. The Whole staff is appointed as per the Shivaji University, Kolhapur and Government of Maharashtra rules and regulations.

Tools for Acquisition

The K.B.P. and M.V.P. College libraries are using the bibliography, expert's opinion, head of department opinion and purchase committee remarks, students' recommendations, syllabus of the courses. Book shops and exhibitions are the primary sources of acquisition. Library department heads and Faculty members use those cited sources and recommend selection. Trade catalogues are also consulted occasionally. Bibliographies, reviews of periodicals, cumulative book indexes, etc., have a lower priority than the other sources.

Library Opening and Closing Hours

The K.B.P. and M.V.P. college library opens from Monday to Friday in the morning session at 7.30 a.m. to 1.30 p.m. and in the evening session at 2.00 p.m. to 5.30 p.m. every day. The library opens on Saturday at 11.45 a.m. to 4.30 p.m. The Reading Room is kept open to all students for whole day. Both college Libraries will be closed on the Government holidays only.

Book Selection Policy

In both the colleges the selection body for library books is the department head and faculty members. Sometimes management of the college does book selection for libraries, while the library committee also occasionally selects books.

Access Services

In the both college libraries always keeps the open access for the students and teachers. The society members and alumni students are also taking the books to their personal

use. The Library also provides the access to management members, D.Ed., B.Ed., M.Phil., NET, SET and Ph.D. students who are coming from the society.

Library Lending Services

The K.B.P. College library issues the two books through computers system at one time to one student and kept for 8 days returning time and for one faculty member 25 books are issued to one faculty for one month. Where as in M.V.P. college library issue the one borrower ticket to one student and one book at one time to one student for 8 days time period. The faculty takes 25 books maximum from the library and for one month period.

Organization of the Collection

Classification

In the K.B.P. College Library the librarian has used the 18th Edition of Dewey Decimal Classification System for classifying the documents and 100 percent documents are classified as per DDC 18th edition scheme and all library collection arranged according to the DDC scheme by all subjects in the library. In the M.V.P. College library the librarian has used the DDC 22nd edition for classifying the books and arranged according to DDC 22nd edition in the library as per subjects.

Documents Cataloguing

The K.B.P. college library is maintained the traditional as well as computer cataloguing and The M.V.P. college library are maintaining subject cataloguing in their library.

Stock Verification

Both college libraries are conducting the stock verification in every year as per the accession numbers and keeping the record and recovering the missing documents and preparing the annual stock verification report and also recovering the missing documents as per rules of the Maharashtra state government. Both libraries are maintaining the withdrawal register to withdraw the lost and damaged documents and books.

Management of Information Services

Services ---

Both college libraries are providing the following services to the learners

1. Book Bank facility to poor students
2. Library facilities to MPSC, UPSC and Ex-students on deposit basis.
3. Inter library loan facility.

4. Ready reference services to any citizens.
6. New arrivals display and issue to learners.
7. Employment news and job orientation information to learners.
8. Display of college news published in local newspapers
9. News paper clipping information services.
10. To Provide Statistical information services to library science learning students. Office, UGC office, Shivaji University, NAAC Office, Maharashtra Government office and Management office.
11. Examination Question-papers and Course Syllabus Providing Services.
12. Educational guidance services
13. Marriage Registration and Change in name information services.
14. Environmental Information services to learners.
15. Information on books published by faculty
16. Information on actual job services.
17. User Orientation Programme

Management Cooperation

Both college Librarians found that the management is cooperative and encouraging them to improve the qualification and quality services in the library.

Services to Enhance Quality

Both college libraries are providing the services as SDI, CAS, educational help, no dues, Photocopying, Computerized circulation, Services on job oriented information i.e. MPSC, UPSC, MBA, banking, Career Oriented Courses etc. To improve the quality of the services, both college libraries are giving priority to computerized services.

Quality Assessment Priorities

Both college librarians gave preference to conduct the Seminars and Workshops for quality assessment techniques under lead college scheme. Both librarians and assistant librarians are attending the National and International Conferences, Seminars, Workshops for their quality development and doing the refresher and orientation courses of library and information science.

Financial Management

10.1 Sources of Library Funds

The K.B.P. College and M.V.P. College Librarians specified "University Grants Commission" as the main source of their budget since both colleges have been recognized as "2 (F) and 12 (B) of UGC Act 1956. Second source of library funds are the fees collected from the students as per rules laid down by Shivaji University, Kolhapur. Third source is Management; it gives the funds for the development of library.

11. Computerization

11.1 Automation

Automation is a very important element in service quality. The K.B.P. College library has used the standard library software which is named as **easy and useful software**. With the help of this software the library completed the computerization. Now, this library working with fully automated library operations. The M.V.P. college library has purchased the **SOUL** software for their library computerization. Now, the library started the data feeding work in the computer. 50% data is stored in the machine. Presently they are working with manual method.

11.2 UGC NRC Centre

Both college libraries has received the UGC Grants under the UGC-NRC Scheme and developed the UGC Network Resource Centre in their library and developed the Internet Network Laboratory for the faculties and students.

Broadband Internet Connectivity

Both college libraries have taken the connection of broadband internet connectivity to supply the services to the faculty members and students. The both Colleges has Subscribed the annual fee of Rs.**11,000/-** for Internet connectivity advance charges to BSNL office, Islampur.

N-List Membership to college library

Both college libraries have subscribed the N-List membership to INFLIBNET Ahmedabad for their college users and fees paid Rs.**5000/-** as the annual fee. The Inflibnet has given the IP Addresses to the both colleges.

Online Services to learners

Both college libraries are providing the online information services to the learners of their institution. Both college Libraries are providing printing facility to the learners.

Special Best Practices in both college libraries

The K.B.P. College library conducting the M.P.S.C. centre for the college and other students. It provides special library services to all students. The M.V.P. College Library conducts the specialized services to women students who are attending the MPSC, UPSC, Remedial Coaching classes for SC, ST, OBC and minorities' students, ex-students. The special feature of college library is the Home Science collection and conducts various competitions for women students and library providing the reading material to these students. Both colleges Librarian's are trying to earn the maximum funds from the UGC on various library aspects.

Conclusion

In accordance with NAAC standards, libraries should establish, promote, maintain, and evaluate a range of quality services that support the colleges, mission and goals. Despite warnings of the UGC and directions to all the colleges, both colleges have undergone NAAC evaluation and colleges have awarded B level and C++ level respectively. Presently, both colleges are preparing for NAAC Re-Accreditation. K.B.P. and M.V.P. College, Libraries are following the so many best Practices in their library about management and services to their libraries. These types of best and ICT based practices are very useful in this modern information era to maintain carrier guidance for user than circulation of books and documents.

The K.B.P. and the M.V.P. College libraries are providing special guidance for completing course and selecting carrier of employment and it is an important educational task. All these above best and ICT based best practices helps library to create special image among students, teachers, lecturers, researchers as well as in the society. With the help of these quality based services the college library creates the good citizens for the nation.

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